

Graph-Augmented Machine Learning Framework for Residue-Level Protein–Peptide Interface Classification Using Structural and Physicochemical Features

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Abstract

Protein–peptide interactions play a central role in molecular recognition, intracellular signalling, enzyme regulation, immune response and therapeutic targeting. Accurate identification of interface residues therefore remains a key challenge in structural bioinformatics, computational biology, and drug discovery. Here, we present an end-to-end computational framework for residue-level interface classification that integrates structural feature engineering, graph-based molecular representation, classical machine learning, and graph neural network (GNN) preparation. The pipeline comprises twenty-one modular Python scripts covering protein structure parsing, residue-level feature extraction, interface labelling, grouped cross-validation, residue contact graph construction, graph topology analysis, graph-augmented machine learning, and GNN-ready dataset preparation. Structural and physicochemical descriptors include the distance of each residue to the peptide centre of mass, local contact density, atomic contact counts, hydrophobicity (Kyte–Doolittle scale), polarity, charge, aromaticity, and B-factor-derived flexibility.

A pilot benchmark dataset of 1,450 residues drawn from four experimentally solved protein–peptide complexes was assembled, of which 87 residues were designated as interface residues using a 5Å contact threshold. Under grouped cross-validation, with protein complex identity serving as the grouping variable, Random Forest achieved the best overall performance (mean F1-score = 0.959 ± 0.049 ; ROC-AUC = 0.999 ± 0.002). Graph-based residue contact representations were subsequently generated and graph topology descriptors including degree, clustering coefficient, betweenness centrality, eigenvector centrality, PageRank, and interface-neighbourhood enrichment were computed and incorporated into graph-augmented models. PyTorch Geometric-compatible datasets were finally produced to support future geometric deep learning experiments.

Taken together, these results demonstrate that interpretable structural descriptors remain highly effective for residue-level interface classification, while the graph infrastructure established here provides a scalable and extensible foundation for GNN-based structural molecular AI.

Keywords: Structural bioinformatics; Protein–peptide interactions; Residue classification; Interface prediction; Machine learning; Random Forest; Graph neural networks; Contact graphs; Computational biology; Structural AI